

D7.14: Exit Strategy Plan

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Executive summary

The exit Strategy for the Pro-Enrich project is the final component in the exploitation effort within the project, which has continuously ensured that the key exploitable results generated in the project were identified, managed correctly and, if relevant, protected. The exit strategy focuses primarily on the key exploitable results as defined in the project and developed also in relation to the business model workshops.

The Pro-Enrich exploitation process has followed two main, interconnected tracks. One track focusing on identifying specific exploitable results and dealing with ownership and IP protection issues. Another track has focused on continuously assessing and evaluating all generated results in order to identify the results with the highest potential for exploitation i.e. key exploitable results and to prepare sustainable business models for these results through business model workshops.

The assessment of the partners based on the project results was that the highest potential for further exploitation is found in the following 3 key exploitable results:

- 1) The rapeseed value stream delivering protein concentrates/isolates for food/feed application
- 2) The tomato value stream extracting a high-value bioactive ingredient (lycopene)
- 3) The citrus value stream extracting a high-value bioactive ingredient (hesperidin)

The exit strategy outlines the IP protection measures and the main exit strategy components for each of these key exploitable results through mainly further research efforts in partnerships and internally (rapeseed protein and tomato/lycopene) and through upscaling and market launch (citrus/hesperidin).

1. OBJECTIVES OF THE EXIT STRATEGY

The Exit Strategy for the Pro-Enrich project is the final component in the exploitation effort within the project, which has continuously ensured that the key exploitable results generated in the project were identified, managed correctly and, if relevant, protected.

The exit strategy focuses primarily on the key exploitable results as defined in the course of the project and developed also in relation to the business model workshops (reported in e.g. D7.12). While the focus of the exit strategy is on the key exploitable results, the exploitation efforts is covering the Results of the project as a whole, as defined in the Grant Agreement:

'Results' means any (tangible or intangible) output of the action such as data, knowledge or information — whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected or not — that is generated in the action, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

The exploitation process has included discussions on IPR issues in alignment with the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement in relation to ownership and adequate protection of results. These issues have been dealt with and the conclusions form the basis of the exit strategy of the project.

Exit strategy focus: The obligation to exploit results

Under the Grant Agreement the exploitation of results is obligatory as stated below:

28.1 Obligation to exploit the results

Each beneficiary must — up to four years after the period (1. May 2018- 31. October 2021) set out in Article 3 — take measures aiming to ensure 'exploitation' of its results (either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing; see Article 30) by:

- (a) using them in further research activities (outside the action);*
- (b) developing, creating or marketing a product or process;*
- (c) creating and providing a service, or*
- (d) using them in standardisation activities.*

Based on this obligation, the exit strategy focuses on the main achievements made in the project resulting in the key exploitable results and on outlining of a strategy for the following aspects:

- Which partner(s) own and are responsible for the exploitation of a given result?
- Which exploitation measures are going to be taken by the partners in the future?

The exit plan thus forms the blueprint for the partners' future efforts based on the results of Pro-Enrich.

In this report, we will outline the exploitation methodology used to identify and manage the key exploitable results, present the key exploitable results as-is and the exploitation measures to be taken in the next steps.

2. PRO-ENRICH EXPLOITATION METHODOLOGY & PROCESS

The Pro-Enrich exploitation process has followed two main, interconnected tracks. One track focusing on identifying specific exploitable results and dealing with ownership and IP protection issues. Another track has focused on continuously assessing and evaluating all generated results in order to identify the results with the highest potential for exploitation i.e. key exploitable results and to prepare sustainable business models for these results through business model workshops.

2.1. IPR & exploitation

In order to ensure that all new knowledge and intellectual property generated by Pro-Enrich was managed correctly, adequately protected and fully exploited, the partners agreed to a transparent and proactive process for each piece of scientific knowledge or innovative technology originating from Pro-Enrich.

The process followed 5 progressive steps that lead to the conclusion of a written exploitation agreement for each result.

- Step 1: Identification of exploitable results
- Step 2: Assessment and establishment of ownership
- Step 3: Assessment and establishment of relevant IPR Protection Measures
- Step 4: Evaluation of exploitation strategy & measures
- Step 5: Concluding exploitation agreement

The progress of the exploitation strategy was continuously monitored by the Steering Committee based on reports from the Exploitation Manager (FBCD).

2.2. Business modelling & exploitation

To support the elaboration of sustainable business models that will support the exploitation and post project sustainability of Pro-Enrich's results and identify exploitable assets, the consortium has worked intensively at each General Assembly to understand and capture the markets and major trends, in which new products/technologies and services are to be implemented. During the course of the project 2 business modelling workshops (M18 and M36) have been executed. It was decided to embed the first round of workshops into the General Assembly Meeting in Koper, Slovenia on the 18th and 19th of November 2019. The first business model workshop was therefore an internal workshop just for project partners.

The objective with this was three-fold:

- 1) To focus the attention of the project participants – and in turn the project – on the key exploitable results of the project and the market requirements for the target compounds and processes.
- 2) To allow interaction between WPs, sharing of ideas, engagement in discussions and thereby focusing on the impact of the project results

- 3) To contribute to the overall direction and work plan of the project at the midterm stage and deliver a basis for project adjustments and (re-)focus.

The 2nd round of business model workshops was held online and embedded in the General Assembly Meeting on the 10th to 12th of May 2021. The workshops were designed to be even more focused and to target the key exploitable results from the project with the highest potential for further exploitation. The assessment of the partners based on the project results was that the highest potential for further exploitation were found in:

- 1) the rapeseed value stream delivering protein concentrates/isolates for food/feed application
- 2) the tomato value stream extracting a high-value bioactive ingredient (lycopene)
- 3) the citrus value stream extracting a high-value bioactive ingredient (hesperidin)

2.3. Exit plan & exploitation

At the final event and GA for the project, the partners discussed the final results emerging from the project and revisited/elaborated on the conclusions of the business model workshop and the exploitation strategy in connection to each result.

This discussion at the final event and commitments made therein forms the foundation for this exit strategy.

3. KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

The Pro-Enrich project set out to demonstrate a new business model for the financial impact and economic potential of high-value components from agricultural side streams, demonstrating how these products can be technically and commercially feasible with both small and large-scale bioprocessing units. So in terms of exploitation and IPR protection, the development of biorefinery processing for maintaining product activity would be expected to generate the main bulk of exploitable results in terms of scalable and commercially viable biorefining solutions demonstrated.

Some of the main areas, where Pro-Enrich expected to go beyond state of art were the following as stated in the exploitation strategy in the very beginning of the project:

- Pro-Enrich will develop protocols for the production of 4 different ingredients with a purity levels that enable their use in the following 4 applications fields: Food, pet food, cosmetics and adhesives
- Pro-Enrich will develop and test gentle processing techniques which will maintain compound functionality.
- Pro-Enrich will address the gaps in knowledge and develop a range of new products based on existing and new knowledge and methods. It will achieve an overall TRL of 4-5 and be ready for scale-up.
- Pro-Enrich will develop and test ways in which highly functional compounds can be achieved from a range of residual feedstocks.
- Pro-Enrich will make use of common residual streams and optimise the use of these by enabling the extraction of valuable, high-quality compounds.

- Pro-Enrich will help standardise the technologies needed and increase opportunities for both small-scale processing and larger commercial enterprises
- Pro-Enrich will develop and test a range of ‘gentle’ processing technologies with no harmful solvents or chemicals, and conduct assessments to ensure health and safety across the entire supply chain.
- Pro-Enrich will develop novel methods for polyphenol extraction using magnetic nanoparticles

The project has to a very large extent – as reported elsewhere – delivered on all of these high-level results and delivered progress beyond state-of-the-art. Throughout the project, the focus has been on pursuing the specific results, which hold the highest potential for exploitation. In the early stages of the project a number of specific technologies were targeted as the main areas of interest as illustrated in table 1 below.

Table 1. Gross list of targeted technologies and results

Value stream	Initially targeted technologies & results (M24)
Rapeseed	Process technology for protein separation and extraction from rapeseed cake/meal in pilot scale
	Process technology for extracting polysaccharides/ dietary fibres from rapeseed cake/meal in pilot scale
	Fractionation (physical separation) of rapeseed hulls from kernels to improve protein yields
Tomato	Process technology extracting lycopene from tomatoes
	Process technology delivering protein concentrate/isolate from tomatoes
	Process technology extracting polysaccharides / dietary fibres from tomatoes
Citrus	Process technology extracting hesperidin from citrus
	Process technology extracting polysaccharides /dietary fibers from citrus
Olives	Process technology extracting polyphenols from olive mill waste-water (OMWW) and pomace using magnetic/modified nanoparticles
	Process technology extracting polyphenols from olive pomace
	Process technology extracting lignin from olive pomace

While efforts continued to develop each of these technologies and resulting end-products, the assessment of the partners based on the project results was that the highest potential for further exploitation is found in the following 3 key exploitable results:

- 4) The rapeseed value stream delivering protein concentrates/isolates for food/feed application
- 5) The tomato value stream extracting a high-value bioactive ingredient (lycopene)
- 6) The citrus value stream extracting a high-value bioactive ingredient (hesperidin)

The selection of these was based both on the technological advances in the project expressed in terms of the TRL-level achieved, but was also based on the potentials in the marketplace for each of the extracted compounds.

Table 2 below outlines the major conclusions on the development stage of each key exploitable result based on the business development workshop in month 36 and the final discussions at the final GA in month 42.

The three value streams and key exploitable results have different TRL levels and therefore different exploitation strategies (see section 5). The rapeseed and tomato value stream key results are to be exploited in further research targeting upscaling and demonstration of the most promising technologies. The technology level and maturity of the citrus value stream is closer to market application.

Table 2. Key exploitable results

	Technology status TRL level achieved	Scalability of processes	Marketable product & target markets
Rapeseed: Protein concentrates / isolates for food/feed	<p>There is a difference between the TRL levels of the technological processes handling hot-pressed vs. cold-pressed rapeseed cake.</p> <p>There is still need for further research before going to demo-scale.</p> <p>TRL LEVELS ACHIEVED:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 (cold-pressed) • 5 (hot-pressed) 	<p>Several upscaling steps will be required to achieve industrial scale..</p>	<p>The markets in e.g. pet food and human consumption can integrate the products and show demand. The focus should be more on the marketable product than the target sector. E.g. protein concentrate vs. isolate, fibres, functionality.</p>
Tomato: Lycopene extraction	<p>The lycopene process will require further research and development before reaching demosc scale</p> <p>TRL LEVEL ACHIEVED:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4-5 	<p>The lycopene extraction process has yet to be developed further.</p>	<p>There are several potential markets for lycopene. The underlying process does not need to be altered much whether it is targeted towards nutritional applications, cosmetics or nutraceuticals. The formulation and the purity/quality of the product are slightly different, while market drivers are very different.</p>

4. IPR PROTECTION MEASURES

4.1. Rapeseed: Protein concentrates/isolates for food/feed/adhesives

The processes developed for cold- and hot-pressed rapeseed are showing good prospects and may qualify for a patent at the next phase of development.

For the development of a patent further tests, trials and analysis need to be performed, in order to confirm and demonstrate the robustness and yield of the processes. The consortium will aim to proceed with developing and industrializing the processes to achieve the required information needed for claiming a patent. We see patentability as a main goal for the further work.

With the conclusion of this project and in regards to the current state of the process, it has been chosen to keep the results close (know-how protection). This is due to the time and costs associated with developing a patent.

4.2. Tomato: Lycopene extraction & Citrus: Hesperidin extraction

For the lycopene and hesperidin extraction several measures have been considered, incl. patentability and trademarks.

Product patent: In this sector, patenting a product is complicated, because we are dealing with natural compounds that already exist in nature thus the novelty is compromised. In certain cases, it is possible to protect by patenting certain products or formulations with a specific application, especially when a particular combination of phytochemicals shows a synergistic effect. However, this has not been proved in Pro-Enrich.

Process patent: In the botanical extract sector in general and in Pro-Enrich in particular, the extraction processes employed are not based on new patented technologies, they are instead based on more innovative and novel use/approach of existing methods. This kind of process is composed of various differential steps and, potentially, it could be studied, whether this new sequence of process steps is novel and can be protected. However, from our experience process patents are quite weak and easy to bypass, only with slight modification of the process. Moreover, sometimes the publication of the process in a patent can serve as inspiration for similar approaches, thus being counterproductive.

Finally, it is also important to consider the cost associated with patents, that sometimes can be considerable when it comes to international patenting.

Trademarks: Natac's business model is based on B2B relations, where trademarks are normally not especially relevant, this is why in our protection strategy trademark registration is only undertaken for very special innovative formulations with particular applications in the market. This approach is normally analysed in advanced stages of development and before entering the market at TRL>9, which has not yet been achieved in Pro-Enrich.

Table 3. Summary of IPR Measures

Key Exploitable Result (KER)	OWNERSHIP <i>SINGLE PARTY/JOINT OWNERSHIP</i>	RELEVANT IPR PROTECTION <i>IPR MEASURES</i> - Patent - Trademark - Design - Trade secret - Know-how	EXPLOITATION MEASURES		EXPLOITATION AGREEMENT CONCLUDED <i>YES/NO</i>
			<i>DIRECT</i> - Further research - Product or process - Service, - Standardisation	<i>INDIRECT</i> - Transfer of ownership - Granting licenses	
Rapeseed: Protein concentrates/isolates for food/feed/adhesives¹	Single party ownership DTI	Know-how	<u>Short term:</u> Further research <u>Medium term:</u> Potential service	<u>Long term:</u> Transfer of ownership Granting licenses	No – not relevant
Tomato: Lycopene extraction	Single party ownership NATAC	Know-how Trade secret	Further research <u>Medium term:</u> Product or process	N/A	No – not relevant
Citrus: Hesperidin extraction	Single party ownership NATAC	Know-how Trade secret	Product or process	N/A	No – not relevant

¹ Adhesives application is a scenario for the HPR biorefinery protein concentrate product, however it has lower estimated market price (€1 to 2 per kg of protein concentrate) and would cause even less favourable market potential.

5. EXIT STRATEGY – KEY COMPONENTS

Key Exploitable Result (KER)	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	EXPLOITATION MEASURES	EXIT STRATEGY
Rapeseed: Protein concentrates/isolates for food/feed/adhesives²	DTI	Further research	STRATEGY: DEMOSCALE DEVELOPMENT IN INTERNATIONAL PARTNERSHIPS DTI as the responsible partner will pursue one or more new R&D projects exploring opportunities to develop the key processes and results towards demo-scale. Several consortium partners have indicated interest to continue the collaboration, including Emmelev, GEA, Tate & Lyle, FBCD and CHIMAR.
Tomato: Lycopene extraction	NATAC	Further research	STRATEGY: INTERNAL DEVELOPMENT & OPTIMIZATION OF PROCESSES The responsible partner NATAC is committed to the further development of the technological processes extracting lycopene from tomato biomass.
Citrus: Hesperidin extraction	NATAC	Product or process	STRATEGY: INTERNAL UPSCALING AND MARKET LAUNCH The extraction process for hesperidin from citrus is considered robust with good yield and purity. The responsible partner NATAC has the internal know-how and capacity to upscale the technology processes including a production facility capable of meeting required market volumes.

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